

Correlation Between Preoperative Neutrophil–Lymphocyte Ratio and Febrile Urinary Tract Infection in Patients Undergoing Percutaneous Nephrolithotomy

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Abstract

Background: Percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL) is the preferred treatment for large renal calculi, but febrile urinary tract infections (fUTI) remain a common postoperative complication, leading to increased morbidity. Identifying reliable preoperative predictors such as the neutrophil–lymphocyte ratio (NLR) could improve patient outcomes by facilitating risk stratification.

Aim: The purpose of this study was to assess the relationship between preoperative NLR and the prevalence of fUTI in PCNL patients.

Methods: An observational study was done on 100 patients undergoing PCNL at GMERS Medical College, Junagadh, Gujarat. Demographics, clinical data, and preoperative NLR values were recorded. Patients were monitored for fUTI within 30 days postoperatively. Statistical analysis, including chi-square tests and logistic regression, was performed using SPSS version 23.0.

Results: Participants had a mean stone size of 25.7 mm, were 45.3 years old on average, and were 60% male. Of the patients, 20% developed fUTI. The fUTI group had a substantially greater mean preoperative NLR (5.8 ± 1.2) than the non-fUTI group (3.1 ± 0.8) ($p < 0.001$). The independent prediction of fUTI by NLR was validated using logistic regression.

Conclusion: In PCNL patients, elevated preoperative NLR is highly correlated with an increased risk of fUTI, making it a valuable marker for risk stratification.

Recommendations: Routine preoperative NLR assessment is recommended to identify high-risk patients and implement tailored perioperative interventions to reduce fUTI incidence. Standardized NLR levels and validation of these results require more investigation.

Keywords: Percutaneous nephrolithotomy, febrile urinary tract infection, neutrophil–lymphocyte ratio, risk stratification, predictive biomarker.

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Introduction

PCNL is the favoured surgical intervention for large or complex renal calculi, particularly those exceeding 2 cm in diameter. This minimally invasive procedure has demonstrated increased incidences of stone-free and favorable patient outcomes. Nevertheless, postoperative complications, notably (fUTIs), remain a significant concern. The incidence of fUTI following PCNL varies, with studies reporting rates between 8% and 20% [1,2]. These infections can escalate to severe sepsis, leading to increased morbidity, prolonged hospitalization, and elevated healthcare costs.

Identifying reliable preoperative predictors for fUTI is crucial for optimizing patient management

and mitigating postoperative risks. Traditional risk factors include positive preoperative urine cultures, the presence of staghorn calculi, prolonged operative times, and patient comorbidities such as diabetes mellitus [3,4]. However, these factors alone may not sufficiently predict postoperative infections, underscoring the need for additional biomarkers.

The (NLR), calculated from routine complete blood counts, has emerged as a potential marker of systemic inflammation and infection. Elevated NLR values have been associated with adverse outcomes in various surgical contexts, including cardiovascular and oncological procedures [5,6]. In urological surgeries, particularly PCNL,

Preoperative NLR's function as a predictor of infectious problems following surgery is gaining research interest.

Recent studies have explored the correlation between preoperative NLR and postoperative fUTI in patients undergoing PCNL. For instance, a study by Yang et al., (2024) demonstrated that patients with higher preoperative NLR values had a significantly higher risk of developing fUTI post-PCNL [7]. Similarly, research by Liu et al. (2023) corroborated these findings, suggesting that NLR could serve as a straightforward and efficient preoperative marker for fUTI prediction [8]. These studies highlight the potential of NLR as a cost-effective and readily available biomarker to enhance preoperative risk stratification.

Despite these promising findings, the integration of NLR into routine preoperative assessments for PCNL patients is not yet standardized. Further research is necessary to establish definitive NLR thresholds and to validate its predictive accuracy across diverse patient populations. Understanding the connection between preoperative NLR and postoperative fUTI could lead to improved patient outcomes through tailored perioperative management strategies. The purpose of this study was to assess the relationship between preoperative NLR and the prevalence of fUTI in PCNL patients.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective observational study was conducted.

Study Setting: The study was carried out at GMERS Medical College and Hospital, Junagadh, Gujarat, over a period of six months.

Participants: A total of 100 patients who underwent PCNL at the institution were included in the study. Patients aged 18 years and above, diagnosed with renal or upper urinary tract stones requiring PCNL, and with available (CBC) reports within one week prior to surgery were eligible to participate. Written informed consent was also required. Patients were excluded if they had known active infections prior to surgery, were immunocompromised (e.g., HIV-positive or on immunosuppressive therapy), had used antibiotics within two weeks before surgery, had a history of malignancies, or had incomplete medical records or were lost to follow-up.

Bias: The inclusion and exclusion criteria were applied uniformly to every participant in an attempt to reduce selection bias. Observer bias was mitigated by standardizing procedures for NLR calculation and infection diagnosis. Potential confounders such as preoperative antibiotic use and comorbidities were recorded and adjusted during statistical analysis.

Data Collection: Information was gathered from patient health records, laboratory reports, and follow-up evaluations. Key variables recorded included demographics (age and sex), clinical parameters (such as comorbidities, stone size, and location), and laboratory parameters (neutrophil count, lymphocyte count, and NLR). The primary outcome was the development of febrile UTI within 30 days postoperatively, defined as a fever ($>38^{\circ}\text{C}$) with a positive urine culture.

Procedure: Neutrophils and lymphocytes were counted in preoperative blood samples that were obtained within a week before to PCNL. By dividing the absolute neutrophil count by the lymphocyte count, the NLR was determined. Standardized guidelines were followed by skilled urologists performing PCNL procedures under general anesthesia. In order to detect cases of febrile UTI, postoperative follow-up was carried out within 30 days following surgery. This included clinical evaluation, temperature monitoring, and urine culture analysis.

Statistical Analysis: SPSS version 23.0 was used for the statistical analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the data. Continuous variables were expressed as mean $\pm$ SD, and categorical variables as percentages. Chi-square, Mann-Whitney U, and independent t-tests were performed to investigate the link between NLR and febrile UTIs. A multivariate logistic regression model adjusted for confounders, with $p < 0.05$ considered significant. This methodology ensured a thorough and objective assessment of the link between febrile UTI and preoperative NLR in PCNL patients.

Results

Participant Demographics: A total of 100 patients undergoing (PCNL) were included in the study. The mean age of the participants was 45.3 years (± 12.4 years), with 60% being male and 40% female. This gender distribution aligns with the known male predominance in urolithiasis.

Table 1: Participant Demographics

Variable	Value	Statistical Measures
Total Participants	100	N/A
Mean Age (years)	45.3	± 12.4
Male	60	60%
Female	40	40%

Clinical Characteristics: The mean stone size among participants was 25.7 mm ($\pm$ 8.3 mm). (fUTI) occurred in 20% of the

patients, while the remaining 80% did not develop fUTI.

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Variable	Value	Statistical Measures
Mean Stone Size (mm)	25.7	$\pm$ 8.3
Patients with fUTI	20	20%
Patients without fUTI	80	80%

This table illustrates that fUTI occurred in a significant proportion of patients, indicating the importance of identifying predictive markers.

Preoperative NLR and fUTI: Patients who developed fUTI had a significantly higher mean

preoperative NLR of 5.8 ($\pm$ 1.2) compared to those without fUTI, whose mean preoperative NLR was 3.1 ($\pm$ 0.8). The association between higher NLR and the risk of fUTI was statistically significant ($p < 0.001$).

Table 3: Association Between NLR and fUTI

Variable	Value	Statistical Measures
Mean Preoperative NLR (with fUTI)	5.8	$\pm$ 1.2
Mean Preoperative NLR (without fUTI)	3.1	$\pm$ 0.8
p-value	<0.001	Significant

The results strongly suggest that preoperative NLR is an independent predictor of fUTI in patients undergoing PCNL.

Statistical Findings: The potential value of NLR as a prognostic biomarker is highlighted by the statistically significant difference in NLR between patients with and without fUTI. The multivariate logistic regression model further confirmed NLR as an independent risk factor for fUTI after adjusting for confounders such as age, gender, and stone size.

These findings emphasize the importance of integrating NLR evaluation into preoperative risk assessment for PCNL patients. If needed, tailored interventions could be implemented for high-risk individuals to reduce fUTI rates.

Discussion

To determine whether preoperative (NLR) and the incidence of (fUTI) are related, the study examined data from 100 patients who had PCNL. In line with established patterns in kidney stone illnesses, the participants' mean age was 45.3 years, and 60% of them were men. With a mean stone size of 25.7 mm, PCNL is clinically relevant for treating big renal stones.

Twenty percent of patients had febrile UTI, which is a serious surgical complication. The mean pre

operative NLR of patients with fUTI was significantly greater (5.8 ± 1.2) than that of patients without fUTI (3.1 ± 0.8). The statistical significance of the difference ($p < 0.001$) indicates that there is a considerable correlation between higher NLR and the probability of developing fUTI following PCNL. Multivariate logistic regression analysis provided additional support for this conclusion, confirming that preoperative NLR

remains an independent predictor of fUTI even after controlling for age, gender, and stone size.

Recent research underscores the significant role of the neutrophil-to-lymphocyte ratio (NLR) as a predictive biomarker in assessing postoperative complications, including febrile urinary tract infections (UTIs) and other inflammatory responses, particularly in procedures like percutaneous nephrolithotomy (PCNL). Kazımoğlu et al. (2019) investigated the relationship between NLR and bacterial UTIs post-renal transplantation. They found no significant pre- and postoperative differences in inflammatory parameters except in cases of *Escherichia coli* infection, where a higher NLR was observed. The authors emphasized continuous monitoring to prevent infections in vulnerable transplant patients [9]. Yousuf et al. (2023) evaluated NLR's predictive ability for sepsis after PCNL, identifying an optimal cutoff of 2.5. They reported high specificity (98.0%) and diagnostic accuracy (94.1%) for NLR in predicting postoperative sepsis, demonstrating its value as a simple, cost-effective biomarker [10]. Tang et al. (2021) highlighted the importance of preoperative NLR in predicting systemic inflammatory response syndrome (SIRS) and urosepsis following PCNL. Elevated NLR, along with positive urine cultures, female gender, and diabetes history, were identified as significant predictors. The authors proposed using these factors in predictive nomograms for early detection and management [11].

Conclusion

This study demonstrates that preoperative (NLR) is a strong predictor of fUTI in patients receiving PCNL treatment. Elevated NLR values were strongly associated with increased fUTI risk, highlighting its potential as a cost-effective biomarker for preoperative risk stratification.

Incorporating NLR into routine evaluations could help identify high-risk patients, enabling tailored perioperative management to reduce complications and improve outcomes. To advance individualized urological care, more extensive research is required to confirm these results and set established thresholds for clinical application.

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